

THE CREATIVE APPROACH OF MANAGING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL AND POST-SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO IMPROVE THE LEVEL OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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Abstract. *This article gives information about the creative and modern ways of learning the English language over Uzbekistan in educational institutions and to improve the rate of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the world. Furthermore, there is given one of the ways how to implement the method in the article.*

Keywords: *children, method, creative method, book, educating, technology, knowledge, skills.*

Last years the President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan pay attention a lot to improve the rating of republic in English language proficiency. At the demand of the present time, the study of foreign languages is becoming important. This situation necessitates the use of much improved methods. In fact, knowledge of a foreign language creates many opportunities for everyone, these opportunities are common in both the field of study and in the field of work.

For example, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 № PD-5117 "On measures to raise to a qualitatively new level activities to promote the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and in the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 19, 2022 №34 "On additional measures to improve the study of foreign languages" it is stated that improving the level of knowledge of foreign languages, as well as reflecting the goals of the development of foreign language teaching.

On January 20, 2023, an expanded meeting was held on the development of the system of teaching foreign languages and vocational training in schools. In his Appeal, the President of Uzbekistan said: "A child, who has mastered a profession and a language at school, will be a great achievement for our society."

Nowadays we can say that there is a rapid development of information and communication technologies, which allows or gives an opportunity to qualitatively raise the level of knowledge of all civilized humanity on earth. With the help of the Internet, Telegram channels and social networks, any information from the original source in all directions has become available to humanity in international languages (English, Russian, Chinese, etc.).

Currently, people sitting at home at a computer, laptop or using a smartphone have the opportunity to look into any corner of the world, watch or read all the world news and achievements in all fields. However, all this information is sanctified in foreign languages. And when translating, distortions are often allowed, when an incorrect translation of one word can

distort the meaning of the entire sentence, or even the entire text. Therefore, in order to be aware of all reliable world events and achievements, it is necessary to know foreign languages, as the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has repeatedly said in his speeches.

To achieve these goals, it is necessary to comprehensively make great efforts to study foreign languages, starting with preschool institutions, schools and universities.

It would not be bad to develop and implement for each stage (preschool institutions, schools, universities) its own unique methodology for learning each foreign language, otherwise we will not achieve great success quickly and efficiently. For example, if we take education in schools, there were times, and even now, when textbooks were changed several times without achieving the desired results.

Inaccuracies, errors, inconsistencies of the studied topic and drawings to this topic, and so on were often allowed in published textbooks.

It is necessary for every family to instill in their children a love for the book from childhood, as the head of our state often says in his speeches. Working with the book lays a solid foundation for the harmonious and comprehensive development of the child and the perception of the world. It is necessary to publish more books with color illustrations, informative and fascinating.

In recent years, some of the young people have experienced great relaxation in their attitudes towards the book. This is due to the fact that mostly young people got carried away and switched to the electronic version of obtaining information using the Internet and social networks. It's a modern disease.

Therefore, it is necessary to develop and implement books with QR codes with voice voicing and explanation of the topic being studied for all stages of training, which will allow the user to independently and quickly (in preschool institutions under adult supervision) fix the topic being studied. This method will allow you to simultaneously use the classic version of obtaining knowledge by reading books and modern achievements in the field of ICT. With the help of this technique, you can return to the times of pre-computer relations to the book.

According to statistics, which a study conducted among 113 countries by EF Education First in 2023, Uzbekistan entered the list of countries with a very low level of English proficiency (93rd place, *table 2*; in 2021 - 87th place, *table1*).

Table 1

EF English Proficiency Index by Country 2021

1. Netherlands 661 Very High	13. Poland 600 Very High
2. Singapore 642 Very High	14. Greece 598 High
3. Austria 628 Very High	15. Slovakia 597 High
4. Norway 627 Very High	16. Luxembourg 596 High
5. Denmark 625 Very High	17. Romania 595 High
6. Belgium 620 Very High	18. Hungary 590 High
7. Sweden 618 Very High	19. Lithuania 589 High
8. Finland 615 Very High	20. Bulgaria 581 High
9. Portugal 614 Very High	21. Philippines 578 High
10. Germany 613 Very High	22. Czech Republic 575 High
11. Croatia 612 Very High	23. Malaysia 574 High

12. South Africa 609 Very High	24. Latvia 571 High
25. Estonia 570 High	37. Cuba 535 Moderate
26. Serbia 567 High	38. Belarus 533 Moderate
27. Nigeria 564 High	39. Russia 530 Moderate
28. Switzerland 563 High	40. Ghana 529 Moderate
29. Argentina 562 High	41. Moldova 528 Moderate
30. Hong Kong 561 High	42. Paraguay 526 Moderate
31. Italy 548 Moderate	43. Bolivia 525 Moderate
32. Spain 545 Moderate	44. Chile 524 Moderate
33. France 541 Moderate	45. Georgia 524 Moderate
34. Ukraine 539 Moderate	46. Albania 523 Moderate
35. South Korea 537 Moderate	47. Honduras 522 Moderate
36. Costa Rica 536 Moderate	48. Uruguay 521 Moderate
49. El Salvador 519 Moderate	61. China 498 Low
50. Peru 517 Moderate	62. Tanzania 496 Low
51. India 516 Moderate	63. Turkey 495 Low
52. Dominican Republic 514 Moderate	64. Nepal 494 Low
53. Lebanon 513 Moderate	65. Bangladesh 493 Low
54. Uganda 512 Moderate	66. Venezuela 492 Low
55. Tunisia 511 Moderate	67. Ethiopia 490 Low
56. Armenia 506 Moderate	68. Iran 489 Low
57. Brazil 505 Moderate	69. Pakistan 488 Low
58. Guatemala 505 Moderate	70. Sri Lanka 487 Low
59. Vietnam 502 Moderate	71. Mongolia 485 Low
60. Nicaragua 499 Low	72. Qatar 484 Low
73. Israel 483 Low	85. Afghanistan 450 Low
74. Panama 482 Low	86. Mexico 447 Very low
75. Morocco 478 Low	87. Uzbekistan 446 Very low
76. Colombia 477 Low	88. Jordan 443 Very low
77. Algeria 476 Low	89. Kyrgyzstan 442 Very low
78. Japan 475 Low	90. Azerbaijan 440 Very low
79. Indonesia 469 Low	91. Myanmar 437 Very low
80. Ecuador 466 Low	92. Cambodia 434 Very low
81. Syria 461 Low	93. Sudan 426 Very low
82. Kuwait 459 Low	94. Cameroon 425 Very low
83. Egypt 454 Low	95. Thailand 423 Very low
84. Mozambique 453 Low	96. Haiti 421 Very low
97. Kazakhstan 420 Very low	104. Tajikistan 397 Very low
98. Somalia 414 Very low	105. Rwanda 392 Very low
99. Oman 412 Very low	106. Libya 390 Very low
100. Saudi Arabia 406 Very low	107. Yemen 370 Very low

101. Iraq 404 Very low	108. DR Congo 367 Very low
102. Ivory Coast 403 Very low	109. Laos 364 Very low
103. Angola 402 Very low	

Table 2

Global Ranking of Countries and Regions 2023

Very high proficiency	High proficiency
1Netherlands(647)	13Poland(598)
2Singapore(631)	14Finland(597)
3Austria(616)	15Romania(596)
4Denmark(615)	16Bulgaria(589)
5Norway(614)	17Hungary(588)
6Sweden(609)	18Slovakia(587)
7Belgium(608)	19Kenya(584)
8Portugal(607)	20Philippines(578)
9South Africa(605)	21Lithuania(576)
10Germany(604)	22Luxembourg(575)
11Croatia(603)	23Estonia(570)
12Greece(602)	24Serbia(569)
Moderate proficiency	25Malaysia(568)
31Honduras(544)	26Czech Republic(565)
32Georgia(541)	27Nigeria(562)
33Belarus(539)	28Argentina(560)
34Ghana(537)	29Hong Kong, China(558)
35Spain(535)	30Switzerland(553)
35Italy(535)	Low Proficiency
35Moldova(535)	64Pakistan(497)
38Costa Rica(534)	65Lebanon(496)
39Albania(533)	66Turkey(493)
39Uruguay(533)	67Sri Lanka(491)
41Bolivia(532)	67Tanzania(491)
41Russia(532)	69Ethiopia(490)
43Cuba(531)	70Brazil(487)
43France(531)	71U.A.E.(486)
45Ukraine(530)	71Panama(486)
45Paraguay(530)	73Mongolia(482)
47Uganda(529)	73Qatar(482)
48Armenia(528)	75Colombia(480)
49South Korea(525)	76Morocco(478)
50El Salvador(524)	77Algeria(475)

51Peru(521)	78Madagascar(474)
52Chile(518)	79Indonesia(473)
53Guatemala(515)	80Ecuador(467)
54Israel(514)	80Syria(467)
55Dominican Republic(512)	82China(464)
56Venezuela(508)	83Azerbaijan(463)
57Nepal(507)	83Egypt(463)
58Iran(505)	85Kuwait(461)
58Vietnam(505)	86Malawi(460)
60Bangladesh(504)	87Japan(457)
60India(504)	88Afghanistan(456)
62Nicaragua(503)	89Mexico(451)
63Tunisia(502)	90Myanmar(450)
Very low proficiency	90Kyrgyzstan(450)
92Palestine(445)	
93Uzbekistan(442)	
94Cameroon(438)	
94Senegal(438)	
96Jordan(431)	
97Sudan(430)	
98Cambodia(421)	
98Haiti(421)	
100Oman(418)	
101Angola(416)	
101Thailand(416)	
101Benin(416)	
104Kazakhstan(415)	
105Somalia(411)	
106Iraq(410)	
107Côte d'Ivoire(409)	
108Saudi Arabia(408)	
109Rwanda(405)	
110Libya(392)	
110Yemen(392)	
112Tajikistan(388)	
113Democratic Republic of Congo(385)	

Analyzing the results of the research conducted by EF Education First over these two or three years, it seems to me that we need to radically change the attitude towards raising the rating of English proficiency. I believe that the Republic of Uzbekistan can and is capable of occupying significantly higher places in the world.

This situation, in my opinion, requires resorting to creative technology of proxy influence and management of the educational process in education through the development of textbooks and textbooks with QR codes. In this progressive and original way, we will simultaneously increase the interest of students in the book.

In order to quickly and effectively achieve the goals set to improve the English language proficiency rating, it would not be bad for professional working groups to deal with this issue by collectively compiling separate preschool, school, and university unified textbooks and manuals on learning a foreign language.

From my perspective that when compiling textbooks and manuals, it is not possible, but necessary to use the method of brainstorming by members of working groups. Because sometimes you can extract a rational grain from unthinkable proposals. These textbooks and manuals should be published under the authorship of the entire working group.

However, this issue of compiling textbooks and manuals can be dealt with alone, having great experience teaching English in universities, educational centers, schools or lyceums.

I believe that my suggestions can be attributed to brainstorming suggestions.

This teaching method covers the management of the learning process, using a creative way of teaching and educational process, and also renews the love of the book.

In addition, I think that this method puts all students on an equal footing, regardless of whether the student is far away in rural areas or in the city, where students have a large selection of tutors. And also, with this method of managing the educational process, the general level of knowledge of students will quickly and significantly increase, starting with kindergarten children (including parents and educators of children) to pupils of schools, lyceums and students of higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan. With such a creative approach, we can safely hope that the youth of Uzbekistan will justify the trust of the President and the Government of Uzbekistan. Young people will be more erudite, intelligent, knowledgeable in at least one foreign language and will make their worthy contribution to improve the rating and make the Republic of Uzbekistan one of the most developed countries in the world in English language proficiency.

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